

RETAILERS PERCEPTION TOWARDS ONLINE SHOPPING

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Abstract:

Few developments have altered India's lifestyle more quickly and more completely than the Internet. Online access has enabled people from all walks of life to bring entire libraries, entertainment venues, post offices and financial centers to a workplace, to a desktop or to a shirt pocket. The Internet's largest and most meaningful impact may very well be on the way consumers shop for everything from gifts, gadgets and groceries to clothing, cars, and cruises. The ease and selection that the Internet provides to shoppers has changed the face of retailing. More and more, consumers visit a store's Web site to make their choices before traveling to the store itself; and in a rapidly swelling tide, many shoppers are bypassing the store altogether and ordering online directly from the Web sites of their favorite brands and outlets.

Key Words: Retailing & Online Access

Introduction:

People love to shop, and advances in online retail now let consumers shop anytime, anywhere. This access is unprecedented—and not just for shoppers; retailers also have 24/7 access to their consumers. As a result, e-commerce has transformed the business model and changed how shoppers approach retail. Despite its momentous effect on shopping behavior, however, e-commerce is far from revolutionary; it's simply an evolution. Many retailers and manufacturers have simply recognized the opportunities created by new technology. (Ashworth, C, 2012). A large percentage of electronic commerce is conducted entirely in electronic form for virtual items such as access to premium content on a website, but mostly electronic commerce involves the transportation of physical items in some way. Online retailers are sometimes known as e-tailers and online retail is sometimes known as e-tail. Almost all big retailers are now electronically present on the World Wide Web. Online marketplaces such as eBay and Amazon Marketplace have significantly reduced financial and reputational barriers to entry for SMEs wishing to trade online. (Grandon, E. Pearson, J. 2004) These marketplaces provide web presence, marketing and payment services and, in the case of Amazon, fulfilment. This allows SMEs to focus on their core competencies e.g. managing supplier relationships. Moreover, SMEs have choices online, as these marketplaces compete with each other (some retailers sell across several marketplaces) and retailers 'own websites. (Burt, S. Sparks, L. 2003). They also compete with paid search providers and others in providing marketing to SMEs.

Scope of the Study: This research article focuses on studying the retailer's opinion towards online shopping. The marketers after analysing various dimensions of E-Marketing provide services to the consumers in shopping online. It makes the retailers to understand how the consumers decide to purchase products and highlights the activities that occur before, during, and after the purchase of the product. Organizations will benefit by developing suitable strategies and choosing the right model to ensure that consumers spend significant time on the organizational websites to make the purchase.

Objective of the Study: The objective of the study is to analyse the retailers opinion towards online shopping along with their demographic profile.

Hypotheses of the Study:

- ✓ H₁ : There is no significant difference between Ownership, Number of visitors, Nature of customers, Nature of Retailing, Geographical reach, Order placement cycle duration, Transportation cycle duration, Warehousing cycle duration with Strategy, Development, Quality, Pleasure, Hygiene, Ethics, Facilities, Contiguity, Varieties, Affirmative, Destructive and Reduction factors.
- ✓ H₂ : The means of Strategy, Development, Quality, Pleasure, Hygiene, Ethics, Facilities, Contiguity, Varieties, Affirmative, Destructive and Reduction factors have no significant difference with Nature of Retailing.

Sample Size:

The questionnaires were sent out to 200 retailers, there were 183 respondents who completed the questionnaire and there were 17 respondents who did not answer the questionnaire. Therefore, there were 183 eligible respondents who completed the questionnaire and these were used for further analysis in this study.

Analysis and Interpretation:

Factor Analysis: The key concept of factor analysis is that multiple observed variables have similar patterns of responses because they are all associated with a latent (i.e. not directly measured) variable. The below table indicates that KMO Measure of Sampling Adequacy test is significant (because the test value is greater than

0.700 at 0.718) and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity is also found to be significant (approx. Chi-square = 2597.943, df = 703, Significance 0.000). This indicates that the dataset is fit to perform factor analysis. Varimax Rotation Technique is used to examine the obtained factors, and all item loadings above 0.50 are considered for the scale in factor analysis.

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.718
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	2597.943
	df	703
	Sig.	.000

Initial communalities are the estimates of the variance in each variable accounted for by all the components or factors. For Principal components extraction, this is always equal to 1 for correlation analysis. Extraction communalities are the estimates of the variance in each variable accounted for by the component.

Communalities			
Short Description of Variables		Initial	Extraction
TRP1	Healthy Competition	1.000	.555
TRP2	Cut the profit margin	1.000	.664
TRP3	Reduce the sales volume	1.000	.588
TRP4	Negative impact	1.000	.615
TRP5	Unhealthy competition	1.000	.503
TRP6	Positive impact	1.000	.482
TRP7	Way of co-operative marketing	1.000	.661
TRP8	Change of strategy	1.000	.731
TRP9	Violation of socio-cultural values	1.000	.673
TRP10	Association of Traditional Retailers	1.000	.634
TRP11	Change of Distribution strategy	1.000	.719
TRP12	Violation of Business ethics	1.000	.696
TRP13	Improvement of customer service	1.000	.590
TRP14	Replacement of traditional retail stores	1.000	.664
TRP15	Employment opportunity	1.000	.702
TRP16	Economic Development	1.000	.803
TRP17	Impact on Entrepreneurship	1.000	.718
TRP18	Store reputation (food handling, safety hygiene)	1.000	.725
TRP19	Store reputation (ethical business practices)	1.000	.694
TRP20	Quality of fruits and vegetables	1.000	.575
TRP21	Range of products	1.000	.687
TRP22	Service quality	1.000	.724
TRP23	Product availability	1.000	.690
TRP24	Pricing	1.000	.794
TRP25	Parking facilities	1.000	.770
TRP26	Enjoyment of shopping experience	1.000	.709
TRP27	Overall cleanliness and hygiene of store	1.000	.608
TRP28	Goodwill	1.000	.608
TRP29	Proximity	1.000	.813
TRP30	Status	1.000	.768
TRP31	Range of Merchandize	1.000	.572
TRP32	Shopping environment	1.000	.524
TRP33	Billing duration	1.000	.553
TRP34	Loose items	1.000	.734
TRP35	Entertainment	1.000	.666
TRP36	Bargain	1.000	.758
TRP37	Credit Availability	1.000	.744
TRP38	Variety of Modes of payment	1.000	.765
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.			

Only those components are considered as principal components which have an eigen value greater than 1. Here, the first twelve components with eigen value of more than 1 is considered for the study, which explains 67.048% of total variance, and the remaining components explain 32.952% of total variance. The below table presents the total variance of the observed variables explained by each of the principal components / factors. For arriving at possible factors from total 38 variables, rotation was converged in 6 iterations through Varimax.

Total Variance Explained									
Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	6.632	17.454	17.454	6.632	17.454	17.454	2.850	7.500	7.500
2	3.427	9.019	26.473	3.427	9.019	26.473	2.752	7.241	14.741
3	2.239	5.891	32.365	2.239	5.891	32.365	2.664	7.010	21.750
4	2.075	5.459	37.824	2.075	5.459	37.824	2.277	5.991	27.742
5	1.888	4.969	42.793	1.888	4.969	42.793	2.062	5.426	33.167
6	1.744	4.590	47.382	1.744	4.590	47.382	2.049	5.393	38.560
7	1.380	3.632	51.015	1.380	3.632	51.015	2.048	5.388	43.949
8	1.361	3.581	54.596	1.361	3.581	54.596	2.006	5.279	49.228
9	1.249	3.287	57.883	1.249	3.287	57.883	1.940	5.106	54.334
10	1.224	3.221	61.104	1.224	3.221	61.104	1.876	4.936	59.269
11	1.173	3.086	64.190	1.173	3.086	64.190	1.547	4.070	63.339
12	1.086	2.859	67.048	1.086	2.859	67.048	1.410	3.709	67.048
13	.996	2.620	69.669						
14	.931	2.450	72.118						
15	.868	2.284	74.402						
16	.822	2.162	76.564						
17	.786	2.070	78.634						
18	.731	1.924	80.558						
19	.644	1.695	82.253						
20	.610	1.606	83.858						
21	.574	1.510	85.369						
22	.541	1.424	86.793						
23	.525	1.380	88.173						
24	.437	1.151	89.324						
25	.420	1.104	90.428						
26	.402	1.058	91.485						
27	.373	.982	92.467						
28	.370	.973	93.440						
29	.355	.934	94.374						
30	.323	.849	95.223						
31	.286	.752	95.975						
32	.277	.728	96.703						
33	.269	.707	97.410						
34	.254	.667	98.077						
35	.220	.579	98.656						
36	.202	.531	99.187						
37	.176	.464	99.650						
38	.133	.350	100.000						

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Rotated Component Matrix^a

S.No	Item Code	Variable	Factor Loadings	Labeled as
1	TRP 9	Violation of socio-cultural values	0.787	Strategy (7.500%)
	TRP 8	Change of strategy	0.718	
	TRP 10	Association of Traditional Retailers	0.640	
	TRP 18	Store reputation (food handling, safety hygiene)	0.506	
2	TRP16	Economic Development	0.828	Development (14.741%)
	TRP17	Impact on Entrepreneurship	0.754	
	TRP15	Employment opportunity	0.731	
3	TRP21	Range of products	0.793	Quality (21.750%)
	TRP22	Service quality	0.721	
	TRP20	Quality of fruits and vegetables	0.668	

	TRP23	Product availability	0.564	
4	TRP34	Loose items	0.820	Pleasure (27.742)
	TRP35	Entertainment	0.761	
	TRP 33	Billing duration	0.699	
	TRP32	Shopping environment	0.560	
5	TRP27	Overall cleanliness and hygiene of store	0.723	Hygiene (33.167)
	TRP26	Enjoyment of shopping experience	0.677	
	TRP28	Goodwill	0.663	
6	TRP12	Violation of Business ethics	0.737	Ethics (38.560)
	TRP13	Improvement of customer service	0.664	
	TRP11	Change of Distribution strategy	0.657	
7	TRP25	Parking facilities	0.782	Facilities (43.549)
	TRP24	Pricing	0.726	
8	TRP 30	Status	0.832	Contiguity (49.228)
	TRP29	Proximity	0.802	
9	TRP 37	Credit Availability	0.833	Varieties (54.334)
	TRP 36	Bargain	0.711	
	TRP38	Variety of Modes of payment	0.540	
10	TRP7	Way of co-operative marketing	0.711	Affirmative (59.269)
	TRP6	Positive impact	0.653	
	TRP1	Healthy Competition	0.569	
11	TRP4	Negative impact	0.744	Destructive (63.339)
	TRP5	Unhealthy competition	0.651	
12	TRP3	Reduce the sales volume	0.739	Reduction (67.048)
	TRP2	Cut the profit margin	0.700	
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis. Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization. a. Rotation converged in 6 iterations.				

Factor 1 – Strategy: The variables TRP9 - Violation of socio-cultural values, TRP8 - Change of strategy, TRP10 - Association of Traditional Retailers and TRP18 - Store reputation (food handling, safety hygiene) constitute factor I with 7.500%.

Factor 2 – Development: The variables TRP 16 - Economic Development, TRP 17 - Impact on Entrepreneurship and TRP 15 - Employment opportunity constitutes factor II with 14.741%.

Factor 3 – Quality: The variables TRP21 - Range of products, TRP22 - Service quality, TRP20 - Quality of fruits and vegetables and TRP 23 - Product availability constitutes factor III with 21.750%.

Factor 4 – Pleasure: The variables TRP34 - Loose items, TRP 35 – Entertainment, TRP 33 - Billing duration and TRP32 - Shopping environment constitute factor IV with 27.742%.

Factor 5 – Hygiene: The variables TRP27 - Overall cleanliness and hygiene of store, TRP 26 – Enjoyment of shopping experience and TRP28 - Goodwill constitute factor V with 33.167%.

Factor 6 – Ethics: The variables TRP12 - Violation of Business ethics, TRP13 - Improvement of customer service and TRP11 - Change of Distribution strategy constitute factor VI with 38.560%.

Factor 7 – Facilities: The variables TRP25 - Parking facilities, TRP 24 – Pricing constitute factor VII with 43.549%.

Factor 8 – Contiguity: The variables TRP30 – Status and TRP29 – Proximity constitute factor VIII with 49.228%.

Factor 9 – Varieties: The variables TRP37 - Credit Availability, TRP 36 – Bargain and TRP 38 - Variety of Modes of payment constitute factor IX with 54.334%.

Factor 10 – Affirmative: The variables TRP 7 - Way of co-operative marketing, TRP 6 – Positive impact and TRP1 – Healthy competition constitute factor X with 59.269%.

Factor 11 – Destructive: The variables TRP4 - Negative impact and TRP 5 - Unhealthy competition constitute factor XI with 63.339%.

Factor 12 – Reduction: The variables TRP 3 - Reduce the sales volume and TRP 2 - Cut the profit margin constitute factor XII with 67.048%

The important demographic of respondents include Ownership, Number of visitors, Nature of customers, Nature of Retailing, Geographical reach, Order placement cycle duration, Transportation cycle duration and Warehousing cycle duration of retail stores through online shopping. These demographic profile of respondents have been tested with factors of retailers perception towards online shopping (Strategy, Development, Quality, Pleasure, Hygiene, Ethics, Facilities, Contiguity, Varieties, Affirmative, Destructive and Reduction) through Analysis of Variance (ANOVA).

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA):

Analysis of variance (ANOVA) is a collection of statistical models used to analyze the differences among group means and their associated procedures (such as "variation" among and between groups), developed by statistician and evolutionary biologist Ronald Fisher. In the ANOVA setting, the observed variance in a particular variable is partitioned into components attributable to different sources of variation. In its simplest form, ANOVA provides a statistical test of whether or not the means of several groups are equal, and therefore generalizes the *t*-test to more than two groups.

H₀ : There is no significant difference between Ownership, Number of visitors, Nature of customers, Nature of Retailing, Geographical reach, Order placement cycle duration, Transportation cycle duration, Warehousing cycle duration with Strategy factors.

ANOVA							
Source of Variance		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig	Result
Ownership	Between Groups	9.906	16	.619	1.107	.352	NS
	Within Groups	92.826	166	.559			
	Total	102.732	182				
Number of visitors	Between Groups	25.250	16	1.578	2.314	.004	S
	Within Groups	113.187	166	.682			
	Total	138.437	182				
Nature of Customers	Between Groups	10.981	16	.686	.982	.479	NS
	Within Groups	116.047	166	.699			
	Total	127.027	182				
Nature of Retailing	Between Groups	4.361	16	.273	1.095	.364	NS
	Within Groups	41.322	166	.249			
	Total	45.683	182				
Geographical reach	Between Groups	14.652	16	.916	.849	.628	NS
	Within Groups	179.031	166	1.079			
	Total	193.683	182				
Order Placement Cycle Duration	Between Groups	18.496	16	1.156	1.441	.128	NS
	Within Groups	133.187	166	.802			
	Total	151.683	182				
Transportation Cycle Duration	Between Groups	29.239	16	1.827	2.321	.004	S
	Within Groups	130.674	166	.787			
	Total	159.913	182				
Warehousing Cycle Duration	Between Groups	40.531	16	2.533	2.526	.002	S
	Within Groups	166.452	166	1.003			
	Total	206.984	182				

NS – Not Significant

S – Significant

From the above table, it can be inferred that Ownership, Nature of customers, Nature of Retailing, Geographical reach, Order placement cycle duration do not have significant difference with Strategy factors whereas Number of visitors, Transportation cycle duration and Warehousing cycle duration have significant difference with Strategy factors.

H₀ : There is no significant difference between Ownership, Number of visitors, Nature of customers, Nature of Retailing, Geographical reach, Order placement cycle duration, Transportation cycle duration, Warehousing cycle duration with Development factors.

ANOVA							
Source of Variance		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Result
Ownership	Between Groups	5.520	12	.460	.804	.646	NS
	Within Groups	97.212	170	.572			
	Total	102.732	182				
Number of visitors	Between Groups	9.416	12	.785	1.034	.420	NS
	Within Groups	129.021	170	.759			
	Total	138.437	182				
Nature of Customers	Between Groups	12.371	12	1.031	1.529	.118	NS
	Within Groups	114.656	170	.674			
	Total	127.027	182				
Nature of Retailing	Between Groups	3.761	12	.313	1.271	.240	NS

	Within Groups	41.922	170	.247			
	Total	45.683	182				
Geographical reach	Between Groups	7.439	12	.620	.566	.867	NS
	Within Groups	186.245	170	1.096			
	Total	193.683	182				
Order Placement Cycle Duration	Between Groups	12.084	12	1.007	1.226	.269	NS
	Within Groups	139.599	170	.821			
	Total	151.683	182				
Transportation Cycle Duration	Between Groups	20.167	12	1.681	2.044	.023	S
	Within Groups	139.746	170	.822			
	Total	159.913	182				
Warehousing Cycle Duration	Between Groups	16.973	12	1.414	1.265	.243	NS
	Within Groups	190.011	170	1.118			
	Total	206.984	182				

NS – Not Significant

S – Significant

From the above table, it can be inferred that Ownership, Number of visitors, Nature of customers, Nature of Retailing, Geographical reach, Order placement cycle duration and Warehousing cycle duration do not have significant difference with Development factors whereas Transportation cycle duration have significant difference with Development factors.

H₀ : There is no significant difference between Ownership, Number of visitors, Nature of customers, Nature of Retailing, Geographical reach, Order placement cycle duration, Transportation cycle duration, Warehousing cycle duration with Quality factors.

ANOVA							
Source of Variance		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Result
Ownership	Between Groups	11.216	16	.701	1.272	.221	NS
	Within Groups	91.516	166	.551			
	Total	102.732	182				
Number of visitors	Between Groups	16.239	16	1.015	1.379	.158	NS
	Within Groups	122.198	166	.736			
	Total	138.437	182				
Nature of Customers	Between Groups	8.636	16	.540	.757	.732	NS
	Within Groups	118.392	166	.713			
	Total	127.027	182				
Nature of Retailing	Between Groups	2.468	16	.154	.593	.886	NS
	Within Groups	43.215	166	.260			
	Total	45.683	182				
Geographical reach	Between Groups	17.490	16	1.093	1.030	.428	NS
	Within Groups	176.193	166	1.061			
	Total	193.683	182				
Order Placement Cycle Duration	Between Groups	11.438	16	.715	.846	.632	NS
	Within Groups	140.245	166	.845			
	Total	151.683	182				
Transportation Cycle Duration	Between Groups	15.854	16	.991	1.142	.321	NS
	Within Groups	144.059	166	.868			
	Total	159.913	182				
Warehousing Cycle Duration	Between Groups	17.807	16	1.113	.977	.485	NS
	Within Groups	189.177	166	1.140			
	Total	206.984	182				

NS – Not Significant

S – Significant

From the above table, it can be inferred that Ownership, Number of visitors, Nature of customers, Nature of Retailing, Geographical reach, Order placement cycle duration, Transportation cycle duration and Warehousing cycle duration do not have significant difference with Quality factors.

H₀ : There is no significant difference between Ownership, Number of visitors, Nature of customers, Nature of Retailing, Geographical reach, Order placement cycle duration, Transportation cycle duration, Warehousing cycle duration with Pleasure factors.

ANOVA							
Source of Variance		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Result
Ownership	Between Groups	13.485	16	.843	1.568	.083	NS
	Within Groups	89.248	166	.538			
	Total	102.732	182				
Number of visitors	Between Groups	14.058	16	.879	1.173	.295	NS
	Within Groups	124.379	166	.749			
	Total	138.437	182				
Nature of Customers	Between Groups	6.985	16	.437	.604	.878	NS
	Within Groups	120.042	166	.723			
	Total	127.027	182				
Nature of Retailing	Between Groups	4.130	16	.258	1.031	.427	NS
	Within Groups	41.553	166	.250			
	Total	45.683	182				
Geographical reach	Between Groups	14.568	16	.911	.844	.634	NS
	Within Groups	179.115	166	1.079			
	Total	193.683	182				
Order Placement Cycle Duration	Between Groups	19.192	16	1.200	1.503	.104	NS
	Within Groups	132.491	166	.798			
	Total	151.683	182				
Transportation Cycle Duration	Between Groups	16.266	16	1.017	1.175	.293	NS
	Within Groups	143.647	166	.865			
	Total	159.913	182				
Warehousing Cycle Duration	Between Groups	31.189	16	1.949	1.841	.030	S
	Within Groups	175.795	166	1.059			
	Total	206.984	182				

NS – Not Significant

S – Significant

From the above table, it can be inferred that Ownership, Number of visitors, Nature of customers, Nature of Retailing, Geographical reach, Order placement cycle duration, and Transportation cycle duration do not have significant difference with Pleasure factors whereas Warehousing cycle duration have significant difference with pleasure factors.

H₀ : There is no significant difference between Ownership, Number of visitors, Nature of customers, Nature of Retailing, Geographical reach, Order placement cycle duration, Transportation cycle duration, Warehousing cycle duration with Hygiene factors.

ANOVA							
Source of Variance		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Result
Ownership	Between Groups	8.275	12	.690	1.241	.259	NS
	Within Groups	94.457	170	.556			
	Total	102.732	182				
Number of visitors	Between Groups	10.100	12	.842	1.115	.351	NS
	Within Groups	128.337	170	.755			
	Total	138.437	182				
Nature of Customers	Between Groups	6.982	12	.582	.824	.626	NS
	Within Groups	120.045	170	.706			
	Total	127.027	182				
Nature of Retailing	Between Groups	1.995	12	.166	.647	.800	NS
	Within Groups	43.688	170	.257			
	Total	45.683	182				
Geographical reach	Between Groups	6.020	12	.502	.454	.938	NS
	Within Groups	187.663	170	1.104			
	Total	193.683	182				
Order Placement Cycle Duration	Between Groups	10.811	12	.901	1.087	.374	NS
	Within Groups	140.872	170	.829			
	Total	151.683	182				
Transportation Cycle Duration	Between Groups	13.265	12	1.105	1.281	.233	NS
	Within Groups	146.648	170	.863			

	Total	159.913	182				
Warehousing Cycle Duration	Between Groups	17.646	12	1.470	1.320	.211	NS
	Within Groups	189.338	170	1.114			
	Total	206.984	182				

NS – Not Significant

S – Significant

From the above table, it can be inferred that Ownership, Number of visitors, Nature of customers, Nature of Retailing, Geographical reach, Order placement cycle duration, and Transportation cycle duration and Warehousing cycle duration do not have significant difference with Hygiene factors.

H₀ : There is no significant difference between Ownership, Number of visitors, Nature of customers, Nature of Retailing, Geographical reach, Order placement cycle duration, Transportation cycle duration, Warehousing cycle duration with Ethics factors.

ANOVA							
Source of Variance		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Result
Ownership	Between Groups	3.598	12	.300	.514	.904	NS
	Within Groups	99.134	170	.583			
	Total	102.732	182				
Number of visitors	Between Groups	12.152	12	1.013	1.363	.188	NS
	Within Groups	126.285	170	.743			
	Total	138.437	182				
Nature of Customers	Between Groups	5.947	12	.496	.696	.754	NS
	Within Groups	121.081	170	.712			
	Total	127.027	182				
Nature of Retailing	Between Groups	3.617	12	.301	1.218	.274	NS
	Within Groups	42.066	170	.247			
	Total	45.683	182				
Geographical reach	Between Groups	13.151	12	1.096	1.032	.422	NS
	Within Groups	180.532	170	1.062			
	Total	193.683	182				
Order Placement Cycle Duration	Between Groups	9.691	12	.808	.967	.483	NS
	Within Groups	141.993	170	.835			
	Total	151.683	182				
Transportation Cycle Duration	Between Groups	22.485	12	1.874	2.318	.009	S
	Within Groups	137.427	170	.808			
	Total	159.913	182				
Warehousing Cycle Duration	Between Groups	21.310	12	1.776	1.626	.088	NS
	Within Groups	185.674	170	1.092			
	Total	206.984	182				

NS – Not Significant

S – Significant

From the above table, it can be inferred that Ownership, Number of visitors, Nature of customers, Nature of Retailing, Geographical reach, Order placement cycle duration, and Warehousing cycle duration do not have significant difference with Ethics factors whereas Transportation cycle duration have significant difference with Ethics factors.

H₀ : There is no significant difference between Ownership, Number of visitors, Nature of customers, Nature of Retailing, Geographical reach, Order placement cycle duration, Transportation cycle duration, Warehousing cycle duration with Facilities factors.

ANOVA							
Source of Variance		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Result
Ownership	Between Groups	5.069	8	.634	1.129	.346	NS
	Within Groups	97.663	174	.561			
	Total	102.732	182				
Number of visitors	Between Groups	4.216	8	.527	.683	.706	NS
	Within Groups	134.221	174	.771			
	Total	138.437	182				
Nature of Customers	Between Groups	8.309	8	1.039	1.522	.152	NS
	Within Groups	118.718	174	.682			
	Total	127.027	182				

Nature of Retailing	Between Groups	2.999	8	.375	1.528	.151	NS
	Within Groups	42.684	174	.245			
	Total	45.683	182				
Geographical reach	Between Groups	7.493	8	.937	.875	.538	NS
	Within Groups	186.190	174	1.070			
	Total	193.683	182				
Order Placement Cycle Duration	Between Groups	6.519	8	.815	.977	.456	NS
	Within Groups	145.164	174	.834			
	Total	151.683	182				
Transportation Cycle Duration	Between Groups	8.326	8	1.041	1.195	.305	NS
	Within Groups	151.586	174	.871			
	Total	159.913	182				
Warehousing Cycle Duration	Between Groups	12.958	8	1.620	1.453	.178	NS
	Within Groups	194.025	174	1.115			
	Total	206.984	182				

NS – Not Significant

S – Significant

From the above table, it can be inferred that Ownership, Number of visitors, Nature of customers, Nature of Retailing, Geographical reach, Order placement cycle duration, Transportation cycle duration and Warehousing cycle duration do not have significant difference with Facilities factors.

H₀ : There is no significant difference between Ownership, Number of visitors, Nature of customers, Nature of Retailing, Geographical reach, Order placement cycle duration, Transportation cycle duration, Warehousing cycle duration with Contiguity factors.

ANOVA							
Source of Variance		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Result
Ownership	Between Groups	6.008	8	.751	1.351	.221	NS
	Within Groups	96.724	174	.556			
	Total	102.732	182				
Number of visitors	Between Groups	26.202	8	3.275	5.078	.000	S
	Within Groups	112.235	174	.645			
	Total	138.437	182				
Nature of Customers	Between Groups	7.104	8	.888	1.288	.252	NS
	Within Groups	119.924	174	.689			
	Total	127.027	182				
Nature of Retailing	Between Groups	1.705	8	.213	.843	.566	NS
	Within Groups	43.978	174	.253			
	Total	45.683	182				
Geographical reach	Between Groups	9.010	8	1.126	1.061	.393	NS
	Within Groups	184.673	174	1.061			
	Total	193.683	182				
Order Placement Cycle Duration	Between Groups	13.343	8	1.668	2.098	.038	S
	Within Groups	138.340	174	.795			
	Total	151.683	182				
Transportation Cycle Duration	Between Groups	19.420	8	2.427	3.006	.003	S
	Within Groups	140.493	174	.807			
	Total	159.913	182				
Warehousing Cycle Duration	Between Groups	29.784	8	3.723	3.656	.001	S
	Within Groups	177.200	174	1.018			
	Total	206.984	182				

NS – Not Significant

S – Significant

From the above table, it can be inferred that Ownership, Nature of customers, Nature of Retailing, Geographical reach do not have significant difference with Contiguity factors whereas Number of visitors, Order placement cycle duration, Transportation cycle duration and Warehousing cycle duration have significant difference with Contiguity factors.

H₀ : There is no significant difference between Ownership, Number of visitors, Nature of customers, Nature of Retailing, Geographical reach, Order placement cycle duration, Transportation cycle duration, Warehousing cycle duration with Varieties factors.

ANOVA							
Source of Variance		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Result
Ownership	Between Groups	14.568	12	1.214	2.341	.008	S
	Within Groups	88.164	170	.519			
	Total	102.732	182				
Number of visitors	Between Groups	18.099	12	1.508	2.131	.017	S
	Within Groups	120.339	170	.708			
	Total	138.437	182				
Nature of Customers	Between Groups	9.688	12	.807	1.170	.309	NS
	Within Groups	117.339	170	.690			
	Total	127.027	182				
Nature of Retailing	Between Groups	4.691	12	.391	1.621	.090	NS
	Within Groups	40.992	170	.241			
	Total	45.683	182				
Geographical reach	Between Groups	19.981	12	1.665	1.630	.087	NS
	Within Groups	173.702	170	1.022			
	Total	193.683	182				
Order Placement Cycle Duration	Between Groups	12.537	12	1.045	1.276	.236	NS
	Within Groups	139.146	170	.819			
	Total	151.683	182				
Transportation Cycle Duration	Between Groups	24.982	12	2.082	2.623	.003	S
	Within Groups	134.930	170	.794			
	Total	159.913	182				
Warehousing Cycle Duration	Between Groups	13.875	12	1.156	1.018	.435	NS
	Within Groups	193.108	170	1.136			
	Total	206.984	182				

NS – Not Significant

S – Significant

From the above table, it can be inferred that Nature of customers, Nature of Retailing, Order placement cycle duration, Geographical reach and Warehousing cycle duration do not have significant difference with Varieties factors whereas Ownership, Number of visitors, Transportation cycle duration have significant difference with Varieties factors.

H₀ : There is no significant difference between Ownership, Number of visitors, Nature of customers, Nature of Retailing, Geographical reach, Order placement cycle duration, Transportation cycle duration, Warehousing cycle duration with Affirmative factors.

ANOVA							
Source of Variance		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Result
Ownership	Between Groups	7.269	11	.661	1.184	.302	NS
	Within Groups	95.463	171	.558			
	Total	102.732	182				
Number of visitors	Between Groups	22.309	11	2.028	2.986	.001	S
	Within Groups	116.128	171	.679			
	Total	138.437	182				
Nature of Customers	Between Groups	18.889	11	1.717	2.715	.003	S
	Within Groups	108.139	171	.632			
	Total	127.027	182				
Nature of Retailing	Between Groups	3.388	11	.308	1.245	.261	NS
	Within Groups	42.295	171	.247			
	Total	45.683	182				
Geographical reach	Between Groups	26.222	11	2.384	2.434	.008	S
	Within Groups	167.461	171	.979			
	Total	193.683	182				
Order Placement Cycle Duration	Between Groups	4.694	11	.427	.496	.904	NS
	Within Groups	146.989	171	.860			
	Total	151.683	182				
Transportation Cycle Duration	Between Groups	17.418	11	1.583	1.900	.042	S
	Within Groups	142.494	171	.833			

	Total	159.913	182				
Warehousing Cycle Duration	Between Groups	16.347	11	1.486	1.333	.210	NS
	Within Groups	190.637	171	1.115			
	Total	206.984	182				

NS – Not Significant

S – Significant

From the above table, it can be inferred that Ownership, Nature of Retailing, Order placement cycle duration, and Warehousing cycle duration do not have significant difference with Affirmative factors whereas Number of visitors, Nature of customers, Geographical reach, Transportation cycle duration have significant difference with Affirmative factors.

H₀ : There is no significant difference between Ownership, Number of visitors, Nature of customers, Nature of Retailing, Geographical reach, Order placement cycle duration, Transportation cycle duration, Warehousing cycle duration with Destructive factors.

ANOVA							
Source of Variance		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Result
Ownership	Between Groups	7.469	8	.934	1.705	.100	NS
	Within Groups	95.264	174	.547			
	Total	102.732	182				
Number of visitors	Between Groups	4.085	8	.511	.661	.725	NS
	Within Groups	134.352	174	.772			
	Total	138.437	182				
Nature of Customers	Between Groups	8.571	8	1.071	1.574	.136	NS
	Within Groups	118.456	174	.681			
	Total	127.027	182				
Nature of Retailing	Between Groups	.747	8	.093	.361	.939	NS
	Within Groups	44.936	174	.258			
	Total	45.683	182				
Geographical reach	Between Groups	8.885	8	1.111	1.046	.404	NS
	Within Groups	184.798	174	1.062			
	Total	193.683	182				
Order Placement Cycle Duration	Between Groups	4.401	8	.550	.650	.735	NS
	Within Groups	147.282	174	.846			
	Total	151.683	182				
Transportation Cycle Duration	Between Groups	12.175	8	1.522	1.792	.081	NS
	Within Groups	147.738	174	.849			
	Total	159.913	182				
Warehousing Cycle Duration	Between Groups	16.807	8	2.101	1.922	.059	NS
	Within Groups	190.176	174	1.093			
	Total	206.984	182				

NS – Not Significant

S – Significant

From the above table, it can be inferred that Ownership, Number of visitors, Nature of customers, Nature of Retailing, Geographical reach, Order placement cycle duration, Transportation cycle duration and Warehousing cycle duration do not have significant difference with Destructive factors.

H₀ : There is no significant difference between Ownership, Number of visitors, Nature of customers, Nature of Retailing, Geographical reach, Order placement cycle duration, Transportation cycle duration, Warehousing cycle duration with Reduction factors.

ANOVA							
Source of Variance		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Result
Ownership	Between Groups	5.404	8	.676	1.208	.297	NS
	Within Groups	97.328	174	.559			
	Total	102.732	182				
Number of visitors	Between Groups	28.151	8	3.519	5.552	.000	S
	Within Groups	110.287	174	.634			
	Total	138.437	182				
Nature of Customers	Between Groups	5.577	8	.697	.999	.439	NS
	Within Groups	121.450	174	.698			
	Total	127.027	182				

Nature of Retailing	Between Groups	3.296	8	.412	1.691	.104	NS
	Within Groups	42.387	174	.244			
	Total	45.683	182				
Geographical reach	Between Groups	5.996	8	.750	.695	.696	NS
	Within Groups	187.687	174	1.079			
	Total	193.683	182				
Order Placement Cycle Duration	Between Groups	18.629	8	2.329	3.045	.003	S
	Within Groups	133.054	174	.765			
	Total	151.683	182				
Transportation Cycle Duration	Between Groups	16.713	8	2.089	2.538	.012	S
	Within Groups	143.200	174	.823			
	Total	159.913	182				
Warehousing Cycle Duration	Between Groups	8.567	8	1.071	.939	.486	NS
	Within Groups	198.417	174	1.140			
	Total	206.984	182				

NS – Not Significant

S – Significant

From the above table, it can be inferred that Ownership, Nature of customers, Nature of Retailing, Geographical reach, and Warehousing cycle duration do not have significant difference with Reduction factors whereas Number of visitors, Order placement cycle duration, Transportation cycle duration have significant difference with Reduction factors.

Independent T Test:

The independent t-test, also called the two sample t-test, independent-samples t-test or student's t-test, is an inferential statistical test that determines whether there is a statistically significant difference between the means in two unrelated groups. The second hypothesis “The means of Strategy, Development, Quality, Pleasure, Hygiene, Ethics, Facilities, Contiguity, Varieties, Affirmative, Destructive and Reduction factors have no significant difference with Nature of Retailing” is tested with Independent T test.

Comparison of Dimensions of Traditional Retailers Perception with Nature of Retailing:

The t-test shows the difference between two groups and in this study, comparison has been done between Nature of Retailing and factors of Traditional Retailers perception (Strategy, Development, Quality, Pleasure, Hygiene, Ethics, Facilities, Contiguity, Varieties, Affirmative, Destructive and Reduction). The interpretation and discussion pertaining to comparison of various two groups are given below.

The first construct (Strategy) contained 4 statements, Second construct (Development) with 3 statements and third construct (Quality) with 4 statements, Fourth construct (Pleasure) with 4 statements, Fifth construct (Hygiene) with 3 statements, Sixth construct (Ethics) with 3 statements, Seventh construct (Facilities) with 2 statements, Eighth construct (Contiguity) with 2 statements, Ninth construct (Varieties) with 3 statements, Tenth construct (Affirmative) with 3 statements, Eleventh construct (Destructive) with 2 statements and Twelfth construct (Reduction) with 2 statements were used for the analysis. Each construct has been analysed with the Respondents Nature of Retailing through independent ‘T’ test.

Group Statistics					
Nature of Retailing		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Strategy	Single Brand	95	3.5316	.90451	.09280
	Multi Brands	88	3.4148	.98472	.10497
Development	Single Brand	95	3.4175	1.04618	.10734
	Multi Brands	88	3.1780	1.14465	.12202
Quality	Single Brand	95	2.9474	.98317	.10087
	Multi Brands	88	2.9631	1.08975	.11617
Pleasure	Single Brand	95	3.4132	1.02545	.10521
	Multi Brands	88	3.2330	.99481	.10605
Hygiene	Single Brand	95	2.9544	1.09438	.11228
	Multi Brands	88	3.0758	1.04157	.11103
Ethics	Single Brand	95	3.4105	1.01578	.10422
	Multi Brands	88	3.1288	1.09851	.11710
Facilities	Single Brand	95	3.2684	1.16192	.11921
	Multi Brands	88	3.1420	1.25017	.13327
Contiguity	Single Brand	95	3.7947	1.08788	.11161
	Multi Brands	88	3.7443	1.14970	.12256
Varieties	Single Brand	95	3.6386	1.07041	.10982
	Multi Brands	88	3.6591	1.05407	.11236
Affirmative	Single Brand	95	3.9474	.79347	.08141

	Multi Brands	88	3.7386	.94071	.10028
Destructive	Single Brand	95	3.2316	.95319	.09779
	Multi Brands	88	3.1875	1.04857	.11178
Reduction	Single Brand	95	3.2632	.88679	.09098
	Multi Brands	88	3.1136	1.12118	.11952

Independent Samples Test										
		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Strategy	Equal variances assumed	1.083	.299	.836	181	.404	.11681	.13965	-.15875	.39237
	Equal variances not assumed			.834	176.405	.406	.11681	.14011	-.15970	.39331
Development	Equal variances assumed	2.342	.128	1.479	181	.141	.23951	.16195	-.08004	.55907
	Equal variances not assumed			1.474	176.128	.142	.23951	.16251	-.08121	.56023
Quality	Equal variances assumed	.712	.400	-.102	181	.919	-.01570	.15324	-.31808	.28668
	Equal variances not assumed			-.102	175.376	.919	-.01570	.15385	-.31934	.28794
Pleasure	Equal variances assumed	.427	.514	1.205	181	.230	.18020	.14956	-.11489	.47530
	Equal variances not assumed			1.206	180.607	.229	.18020	.14938	-.11456	.47496
Hygiene	Equal variances assumed	.463	.497	-.767	181	.444	-.12137	.15821	-.43354	.19080
	Equal variances not assumed			-.769	180.863	.443	-.12137	.15791	-.43295	.19021
Ethics	Equal variances assumed	.737	.392	1.803	181	.073	.28174	.15629	-.02665	.59012
	Equal variances not assumed			1.797	176.762	.074	.28174	.15676	-.02762	.59110
Facilities	Equal variances assumed	1.451	.230	.709	181	.479	.12638	.17830	-.22545	.47820
	Equal variances not assumed			.707	177.027	.481	.12638	.17881	-.22649	.47924
Contiguity	Equal variances assumed	.014	.905	.305	181	.761	.05042	.16541	-.27597	.37681

	Equal variances not assumed			.304	177.898	.761	.05042	.16577	-.27670	.37754
Varieties	Equal variances assumed	.378	.540	-.130	181	.896	.02049	.15721	-.33070	.28971
	Equal variances not assumed			-.130	180.316	.896	.02049	.15712	-.33052	.28953
Affirmative	Equal variances assumed	1.081	.300	1.627	181	.106	.20873	.12833	-.04448	.46194
	Equal variances not assumed			1.616	170.800	.108	.20873	.12916	-.04623	.46369
Destructive	Equal variances assumed	1.298	.256	.298	181	.766	.04408	.14798	-.24790	.33606
	Equal variances not assumed			.297	175.820	.767	.04408	.14852	-.24903	.33719
Reduction	Equal variances assumed	6.480	.012	1.004	181	.317	.14952	.14888	-.14425	.44329
	Equal variances not assumed			.995	165.583	.321	.14952	.15021	-.14705	.44609

Strategy (H₁):

H₀ : The means of Strategy and Nature of Retailing are not significantly different.

H₁ : The means of Strategy and Nature of Retailing are significantly different.

Levene's Test for Equality of Variances (Homogeneity) result shows that significant value that is 0.299 which means both groups are heterogeneous group so t-test for equal variance assumed is considered. Here the mean value of Strategy of Single brand is 353.16 and that of Multi brands is 341.48 the difference between the two is 11.68 which is insignificant. Based on the result generated by SPSS, the significant value is 0.404 and it is greater than 0.05 so accept null hypothesis. Hence there is no significant difference between the two means i.e. the Strategy towards Single brand and Multi brands.

Development (H₂):

H₀ : The means of Development and Nature of Retailing are not significantly different.

H₁ : The means of Development and Nature of Retailing are significantly different.

Levene's Test for Equality of Variances (Homogeneity) result shows that significant value that is 0.128 which means both groups are heterogeneous group so t-test for equal variance assumed is considered.

Here the mean value of Development of Single brand is 341.75 and that of Multi brands is 317.80 the difference between the two is 23.95 which is insignificant. Based on the result generated by SPSS, the significant value is 0.141 and it is greater than 0.05 so accept null hypothesis. Hence there is no significant difference between the two means i.e. the Development towards Single brand and Multi brands.

Quality (H₃):

H₀ : The means of Quality and Nature of Retailing are not significantly different.

H₁ : The means of Quality and Nature of Retailing are significantly different.

Levene's Test for Equality of Variances (Homogeneity) result shows that significant value that is 0.400 which means both groups are heterogeneous group so t-test for equal variance assumed is considered. Here the mean value of Quality of Single brand is 294.74 and that of Multi brands is 296.31 the difference between the two is 01.57 which is insignificant. Based on the result generated by SPSS, the significant value is 0.919 and it is greater than 0.05 so accept null hypothesis. Hence there is no significant difference between the two means i.e. the Quality towards Single brand and Multi brands.

Pleasure (H₄):

H₀ : The means of Pleasure and Nature of Retailing are not significantly different.

H₁ : The means of Pleasure and Nature of Retailing are significantly different.

Levene's Test for Equality of Variances (Homogeneity) result shows that significant value that is 0.514 which means both groups are heterogeneous group so t-test for equal variance assumed is considered. Here the mean value of Pleasure of Single brand is 341.32 and that of Multi brands is 323.30 the difference between the two is

18.02 which is insignificant. Based on the result generated by SPSS, the significant value is 0.230 and it is greater than 0.05 so accept null hypothesis. Hence there is no significant difference between the two means i.e. the Pleasure towards Single brand and Multi brands.

Hygiene (H5):

H₀ : The means of Hygiene and Nature of Retailing are not significantly different.

H₁ : The means of Hygiene and Nature of Retailing are significantly different.

Levene's Test for Equality of Variances (Homogeneity) result shows that significant value that is 0.497 which means both groups are heterogeneous group so t-test for equal variance assumed is considered. Here the mean value of Hygiene of Single brand is 295.44 and that of Multi brands is 307.58 the difference between the two is 12.13 which is insignificant. Based on the result generated by SPSS, the significant value is 0.444 and it is greater than 0.05 so accept null hypothesis. Hence there is no significant difference between the two means i.e. the Hygiene towards Single brand and Multi brands.

Ethics (H6):

H₀ : The means of Ethics and Nature of Retailing are not significantly different.

H₁ : The means of Ethics and Nature of Retailing are significantly different.

Levene's Test for Equality of Variances (Homogeneity) result shows that significant value that is 0.392 which means both groups are heterogeneous group so t-test for equal variance assumed is considered. Here the mean value of Ethics of Single brand is 341.05 and that of Multi brands is 312.88 the difference between the two is 28.17 which is insignificant. Based on the result generated by SPSS, the significant value is 0.073 and it is greater than 0.05 so accept null hypothesis. Hence there is no significant difference between the two means i.e. the Ethics towards Single brand and Multi brands.

Facilities (H7):

H₀ : The means of Facilities and Nature of Retailing are not significantly different.

H₁ : The means of Facilities and Nature of Retailing are significantly different.

Levene's Test for Equality of Variances (Homogeneity) result shows that significant value that is 0.230 which means both groups are heterogeneous group so t-test for equal variance assumed is considered. Here the mean value of Facilities of Single brand is 326.84 and that of Multi brands is 314.20 the difference between the two is 12.63 which is insignificant. Based on the result generated by SPSS, the significant value is 0.479 and it is greater than 0.05 so accept null hypothesis. Hence there is no significant difference between the two means i.e. the Facilities towards Single brand and Multi brands.

Contiguity (H8):

H₀ : The means of Contiguity and Nature of Retailing are not significantly different.

H₁ : The means of Contiguity and Nature of Retailing are significantly different.

Levene's Test for Equality of Variances (Homogeneity) result shows that significant value that is 0.905 which means both groups are heterogeneous group so t-test for equal variance assumed is considered. Here the mean value of Contiguity of Single brand is 379.47 and that of Multi brands is 374.43 the difference between the two is 05.04 which is insignificant. Based on the result generated by SPSS, the significant value is 0.761 and it is greater than 0.05 so accept null hypothesis. Hence there is no significant difference between the two means i.e. the Contiguity towards Single brand and Multi brands.

Varieties (H9):

H₀ : The means of Varieties and Nature of Retailing are not significantly different.

H₁ : The means of Varieties and Nature of Retailing are significantly different.

Levene's Test for Equality of Variances (Homogeneity) result shows that significant value that is 0.540 which means both groups are heterogeneous group so t-test for equal variance assumed is considered. Here the mean value of Varieties of Single brand is 363.86 and that of Multi brands is 365.91 the difference between the two is 02.04 which is insignificant. Based on the result generated by SPSS, the significant value is 0.896 and it is greater than 0.05 so accept null hypothesis. Hence there is no significant difference between the two means i.e. the Varieties towards Single brand and Multi brands.

Affirmative (H10):

H₀ : The means of Affirmative and Nature of Retailing are not significantly different.

H₁ : The means of Affirmative and Nature of Retailing are significantly different.

Levene's Test for Equality of Variances (Homogeneity) result shows that significant value that is 0.300 which means both groups are heterogeneous group so t-test for equal variance assumed is considered. Here the mean value of Affirmative of Single brand is 394.74 and that of Multi brands is 373.86 the difference between the two is 20.87 which is insignificant. Based on the result generated by SPSS, the significant value is 0.106 and it is greater than 0.05 so accept null hypothesis. Hence there is no significant difference between the two means i.e. the Affirmative towards Single brand and Multi brands.

Destructive (H11):

H₀ : The means of Destructive and Nature of Retailing are not significantly different.

H₁ : The means of Destructive and Nature of Retailing are significantly different.

Levene's Test for Equality of Variances (Homogeneity) result shows that significant value that is 0.256 which means both groups are heterogeneous group so t-test for equal variance assumed is considered. Here the mean value of Destructive of Single brand is 323.16 and that of Multi brands is 318.75 the difference between the two is 04.40 which is insignificant. Based on the result generated by SPSS, the significant value is 0.766 and it is greater than 0.05 so accept null hypothesis. Hence there is no significant difference between the two means i.e. the Destructive towards Single brand and Multi brands.

Reduction (H12):

H₀ : The means of Reduction and Nature of Retailing are not significantly different.

H₁ : The means of Reduction and Nature of Retailing are significantly different.

Levene's Test for Equality of Variances (Homogeneity) result shows that significant value that is 0.012 which means both groups are heterogeneous group so t-test for equal variance assumed is considered. Here the mean value of Reduction of Single brand is 326.32 and that of Multi brands is 311.36 the difference between the two is 14.95 which is insignificant. Based on the result generated by SPSS, the significant value is 0.317 and it is greater than 0.05 so accept null hypothesis. Hence there is no significant difference between the two means i.e. the Reduction towards Single brand and Multi brands.

Conclusion:

The success of online marketing is not the fastness, but abundant brands, variety, size, and cheap cost. All these factors cannot be given to the customer once and not in the followed purchase. All these factors are to be cherished by the customers every now and then when they make purchase. The retailers of online marketing have proved to be competitive, diligent in breaking the traditional shopping habits of the people. If the sustained strategies are propelled with adequate changes over time, the million dollar business would be the online marketing in the years to come.

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